

Entwined forces in quantised space

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In the past some physicists speculated that the strong force (classic interpretation) and the gravitational force are the same force. They reasoned that the difference in strength between the 2 forces is caused by the different scale sizes the measurements were done to detect the strength of the force. In other words, is the hypothesis correct?

Introduction

In 1687 the [universal force of gravity](#) was described by Isaac Newton as an attracting force between 2 masses (matter). But in 1915 Albert Einstein published his interpretation of the origin of the force of gravity (the theory of [general relativity](#)). Einstein's concept implicates that gravity isn't an attracting force or even a push force from vacuum space around. Gravity is the consequence of the geometry (curvature) of space under influence of the existence of matter.

The problem with Einstein's interpretation is that matter forces space itself to curve around the matter. But the whole volume of the universe is space. In other words, the concept of space in Einstein's theory of general reality is not in line with what we observe. In [relational reality](#) we observe that matter moves inside space, actually the whole volume of the universe. In other words, Einstein's interpretation of the force of gravity is not well suited to answer the question if gravity and the strong force are the same. So the inquiry it is about Newtonian gravity and the classical interpretation of the strong force (not the quark/gluon concept in the Standard model).

At the scale size of rest mass carrying particles – like the proton – relational reality is described with the help of the basic quantum fields. So it is reasonable to use (one of) the conceptual framework of quantum field theory to create “pictures” about what is going on at the smallest scale size of relational reality (= phenomenological reality).

Rest mass

Einstein's famous equation $E = m c^2$ is about the equivalence of free energy (E) and mass (m). The equation shows that mass (m) is a local concentration of free energy (E). The consequence is that if we want to reverse the concentrated mass into free energy again we have to multiply the

amount of mass with the square of the speed of light (c^2). It indicates that free energy is directly related to the variance of surface area. In other words, within a volume of vacuum space we can concentrate every single quantum of energy to become part of a local surplus of energy. A local surplus of energy that originates from the volume of vacuum space around the surplus (the deficit).

In vacuum space the universal scalar field (Higgs field) is perfectly flat. That means that every scalar has exactly the same magnitude. Therefore every energy fluctuation (amplitude) in vacuum space is generated by the universal electric field and its corresponding magnetic field (together termed *electromagnetic field*). We know that a rest mass carrying particle like a proton is stable. It doesn't de-concentrate its local amount of energy so the concentrated amount of energy has created a stable energy state. It is like the process of concentration has passed a certain threshold. And beyond the threshold too, otherwise only a slight decrease of energy will force the concentrated energy to be redistributed in vacuum space (like the continuous increase/decrease of electromagnetic amplitudes).

figure 1

The “act” of energy concentration originates from the spherical shape forming mechanism (scalar mechanism) inside every unit of quantised space. Every unit tries to minimise its surface area and the “struggle” of all these units results in local concentrations of energy.^{[1][2]} So I can imagine a volume in vacuum space where the involved units “push” a part of their surplus of surface area (energy) towards the centre of the volume.

I have drawn the volume in figure 1 (red dotted sphere A) and the extended volume that create the surplus of energy beyond the threshold (the black dotted sphere B). The

result of the concentration is the emergence of particle M in the centre of the image. So what is the threshold?

The difference between the amplitudes of the electromagnetic field and a rest mass carrying particle are the magnitudes of the scalars of the local Higgs field. The sphere is the only true scalar in 3D geometry so it is easy to determine the increase of the deformation of the scalar of a unit of quantised space (figure 2).

figure 2

In vacuum space every scalar of the Higgs field has exactly the same magnitude. In other words, in the primordial universe ($t = >13,7$ billion years) every scalar in our universe has exactly the same radius ($r_s = 1.0$). The consequence is that the Higgs field in vacuum space manifests itself as a lattice of spheres (figure 3). Decreasing the radius of one scalar is only possible if a huge amount of units around will force the unit of the scalar to deform its shape beyond the threshold. Figure 2 shows the simple relation between radius and resistance against deformation. Note that a decreased scalar means a decrease of the surface area of the scalar. So it is easier to further deform a unit with a decreased scalar inside than the opposite, decreasing the surface area of the unit (energy well).

figure 3

A rest mass carrying particle like the proton is stable. Therefore it is reasonable to conclude that every rest mass carrying particle has at least one decreased scalar inside.

The lattice of the Higgs field is in rest in relation to the motion of the phenomena, like e.g. particles. The consequence is that there is an energy transfer from the decreased scalar in the centre of the particle – in the direction of the motion – to another scalar. It shows that the surplus of energy – the black dotted circle B in figure 1 – must be large enough to facilitate “the jump”.

References:

1. S.E. Grimm (2020); “On the construction of the properties of discrete space”
<https://zenodo.org/records/3909268>
 2. S.E. Grimm (2025); “On quantitative relations”
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Newtonian gravity

Figure 3 shows the lattice of the Higgs field in vacuum space (every scalar has exactly the same radius). The correspondence with the origin of the existence of 1 dimensional vectors is striking (see [Newton’s cradle](#)). So what will be the consequence if one or more scalars of the Higgs field decrease their radius? Because in the centre of a rest mass carrying particle exists a decreased scalar.

Figure 4 shows a rest mass carrying particle. The units of quantised space are drawn in a schematic way (cubes) and the decreased scalar in the centre of the particle is the red sphere. Other scalars are not drawn. In vacuum space every scalar has 12 points of contact with its adjacent scalars. But the scalars of the units around the decreased scalar have only 11 points of contact. The consequence is a vectorisation of all the scalars around the particle (the schematic red arrows). These vectors are super positioned on the vectors of the magnetic field in vacuum space. The universal electric field and the magnetic field are corresponding fields thus the vectorisation influences the shape of the units.

The increasing influence – actually energy “density” – is symbolised with the help of concentric shells (units) around the particle in vacuum space (grey rasterised). In other words, the local universal electric field is “curved” under influence of the vectorisation of the Higgs field in

vacuum space.^[3] Note that what we observe and measure in physics is not the underlying creating reality of our universe. What we observe and measure are the mutual mathematical relations between the units of quantised space. It means that the particle in figure 4 shows up during experiments as a tiny moving sphere in relational reality while the underlying creating reality doesn't move at all. The underlying reality – quantised space – is a rest frame.

figure 4

Figure 4 shows that Einstein's curved spacetime doesn't exist. The hypothetical curvature of space is just the resultant "curvature" of the universal electric field (the grey rasterised concentric spheres). The resultant curvature is caused by the vectors that are created as the result of the vectorisation of the flat Higgs field around the decreased scalar of the rest mass carrying particle. It shows that gravity (red arrows) is a vector force – like Newtonian gravity – from vacuum space around matter. Moreover, the vectorisation of vacuum space around the rest mass carrying particle is equal to the magnitude of a scalar $r_s = 1.0$ (see figure 2). Note that the gravitational vector field is always "attached" to the rest mass carrying particle.

The "picture" of the resultant curvature of the universal electric field is reliable because gravitational waves propagate in vacuum space with the speed of light. In other words, gravitational waves are manifestations of large scale disturbances of the universal electric field. In line with the absence of not-decreased scalars everywhere within the boundary of a black hole.^[3]

References:

3. S.E. Grimm (2024); "On resultant motion in discrete space" <https://zenodo.org/records/11193931>

The strong force

We know about the existence of the strong force (classical interpretation) because of the experiments with the help of particle colliders. Smashing protons together from opposite directions reveals the existence of a strong repulsive force between protons. In other words, I can draw 2 protons that are nearing each other (figure 5). The image is similar to figure 4 although I haven't draw the schematic units of quantised space (the cubes in figure 4).

The image shows why the gravitational force is so weak in relation to the strength of the strong force. Because its influence is based on the shielding of gravitational vectors (the red lines that are pointing to the decreased scalar of each rest mass carrying particle). The consequence is that the gravitational force between 2 rest mass carrying particles is always less than $\frac{1}{2}$ the magnitudes of the vectors of one particle at a certain distance (red triangles minus the black triangles).

figure 5

Figure 5 also shows that the gravitational force cannot be equal to the strong force because the range of the strong force is really limited (in practise about 3 – 2 times the diameter of a proton). However, the concentric shells (grey rasterised) around the proton reflect the energy density of the local universal electric field (see figure 4). Its range is visible in the diagram of the classical interpretation of the strong force. See figure 6.

figure 6

The diagram in figure 6 represents the influence of the strong force and the dotted horizontal line (red) shows the tunnel effect if 2 protons collide each other at the right position (figure 5). Because the energy density around the proton that is created by the vectorisation of the Higgs field around the proton decreases in correspondence with the decrease of the mutual distance of both particles (relation between the red and black triangles/vectors).

In other words, the strong force emerges from the local energy density of the universal electric field around a rest mass carrying particle. An increase of the local topological deformation of the involved units of quantised space towards the particle that is equal to the progress of the red curve in figure 6.

Conclusion

Although the strong force (classical interpretation) isn't equal to the force of gravity, it is obvious that the strong force reflects the force of gravity because the gravitational vectors are the cause behind the increasing energy density of the universal electric field in vacuum space around the particle (figure 6).

Therefore we are also confronted with the question how the present categorisation of the forces – gravitational force, electromagnetic force, weak force and strong force – is still a realistic categorisation. Because a force is directly related to the dynamical energy transformations of the universal electric field and its corresponding magnetic field. A unification of these 4 forces is inevitable.